

Pedagogical Principles Of Using Integrated Education In Primary School

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Annotation: This article describes the observation of integrated lessons, the scientific views of thinkers based on foreign experience, and the technology for organizing integrated lessons.

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INTRODUCTION

Before organizing integrated lessons in primary school, state requirements should also be studied. That is, it is necessary to determine the criteria for the child's knowledge, skills, qualifications and development status, to assess the level of development and achievements of primary school students, to ensure the individual development of the child, the quality of personnel training, the level of requirements for the content of education, and the skills and qualifications of parents related to the development of the child.

Integration is the ability to naturally interconnect the topics of academic subjects and sections based on leading ideas and evidence, which reveal the deep, consistent, and multifaceted aspects of the processes and events being studied. In an integrated lesson, concepts used in several subjects are interrelatedly instilled. For example: in a mathematics lesson, a child learns numbers, and can

apply this knowledge in other subjects. In each subject, recognizing numbers to find the page of a book, in native language lessons to do exercises in numbers, in technology subjects to measure dimensions correctly, mathematical knowledge is necessary in all such subjects.

In order to increase interest in subjects, it is necessary for the teacher to be thoroughly prepared for each subject, to approach it based on innovative technologies, taking into account the individual characteristics of children. The primary school is the foundation of knowledge in a child's life. Therefore, it is an important factor for primary school teachers to be able to interest students in each subject and to be prepared in accordance with the requirements of the time.

The integrated study of subjects creates a basis for the child to find his place in the future and increase his self-confidence among people. During the lessons, each topic should be introduced not only

theoretically, but also practically. This increases the level of knowledge of children, helps to improve skills such as how to apply this knowledge in life.

In integrated education, the teacher should focus on expanding the worldview of students. This certainly requires a high level of knowledge from the teacher. A teacher is a profession that requires constant research and expanding the level of knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the time. Nowadays, science and technology are developing rapidly, and therefore the teacher must be able to use all technical means (such as computers, projectors, tablets). When using innovative technology in the lessons, it is also important to use integrated educational tools.

The philosopher-humanist Comenius also expressed a number of ideas in the integrated education system. Comenius was one of the first to create laws related to the education system, to solve questions that previous pedagogy could not answer. Comenius called for the connection of students' minds through objects and phenomena in the world and their explanation. Comenius expressed the following ideas about prospective education: "Everything that is interconnected must be taught in the same connection." This is a concept inherent in the methodology of integrated education. These ideas of Comenius caused positive views in the general public of his time. The more effective and correct solution of this interpretation was proven by **Comenius**.

At the same time, I.F. Herbart also tried to justify the necessity of integration in the pedagogical process. During his studies, he identified 4 stages of integration. They are as follows:

- Clarity
- Association
- System
- Method

He considered these 4 stages to be the main part of integration during his studies and stated that in the

process of organizing integrated lessons, the stages mentioned above complement each other.

If we look at Herbart's studies, the stages of clarity and association are considered to be the only stages aimed at acquiring knowledge for students of junior school age. The system and method serve as the main bridge for connecting previously learned things with each other and for mastering new knowledge.

Having carried out a number of works in the organization of education and upbringing, Ushinsky provided a basis for the didactic significance of the connection between the objects and phenomena being studied. In his work "Man - the Subject of Education", he draws conclusions from various associative connections that reflect the objective relationships of the real world and phenomena of things. In Ushinsky's theory, the idea of interdisciplinary connections appeared as part of the general problem of the systemic nature of education. It was based on the interdependence of objects and phenomena in the system of general sciences, which led to the expansion of students' knowledge, the development of their worldview, the growth or formation of logical thinking. Thus, scientists and educators of the 17th-19th centuries considered the integrative concept in their theories and the field of education based on such a system as a necessity that was reflected in the desire to reflect the interconnectedness of the real world, to unite the studied topics and phenomena under a single bridge, which should ensure mutual harmony in their views and theories.

An integrated lesson differs from ordinary lessons in:

- clarity, conciseness, dense scope of educational material;
- comprehensive logical conditioning of the subjects being integrated at each stage of the lesson;
- the presence of a wide range of information in the educational material provided.

Thus, the effectiveness of an integrated lesson requires a thorough preparation of the form of education in a correct, psycho-pedagogically based manner, based on a thorough analysis of all three types: educational, educational, developmental goals. Cross-subject integration is also possible only in a pedagogical team where a healthy environment, mutual respect and creative cooperation reign. The advantages of an integrated lesson are as follows:

1. In this type of activity, the child begins to imagine the world as a whole, as a whole.
2. The child's potential develops, he begins to study the environment with great interest, events begin to prompt him to find a logical, intellectual, causal solution in his mind. As a result, communication skills, the ability to compare and contrast, generalize and draw conclusions develop.
3. The form of the lesson is interesting due to its non-standard nature - the developmental goal is provided at a particularly high level in such lessons.
4. The teacher's creativity is one of the main factors that increase his professional competence.

In the conclusion, Science textbooks are considered the most necessary tool in the implementation of integrated lessons in primary grades. Because the textbook is the most important tool for students. It not only helps in mastering the educational material during the lesson, but also helps to arouse the child's interest in this subject and further develop his passion for natural sciences.

REFERENCES:

- 1.R.A. Mavlonova va boshq . • Boshlang'ich ta'limning integratsiyalashgan pedagogikasi • T., TDPU, 2007.
- 2.B.D.Jonibekovna Boshlang'ich sinflarda integratsiyalashgan darslarning maqsad va vazifalari hamda fanlararo aloqalarning ahamiyati; Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary studeies (Cargis)2022

3.<http://www.genderi.org/1-integratsiya-haqida-umumiy-tushuncha-boshlangich-talim-integ.html?page=2>

4.<https://azkurs.org/boshlangich-talim-tizimida-fanlararo-integratsiyaning-ahamiyat.html>